

An Analysis of Consumption Expenditure of Farmers in Border Areas of Rural Punjab

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Abstract

The main objective of paper is to analyze consumption expenditure patterns among farmers in border areas of rural Punjab, using primary data collected from 423 households through stratified random sampling. The results reveal that an average farm household spends Rs.540090.07 annually on consumption. The household and per capita consumption expenditure increase significantly with farm size, with large farmers spending more on durables, services, and socio-religious activities, while the marginal and small farmers concentrate their limited resources on non-durable essentials such as foodgrains and milk products. The average propensity to consume is above unity for the smaller farmers, indicating consumption beyond income and dependence on borrowing. The marked inequalities in consumption distribution are evident, reflected in high Gini coefficients, especially among semi-medium and large farmers. These findings corroborate existing studies highlighting the persistent consumption disparities driven by farm size in Punjab agriculture. Addressing these inequalities requires targeted policies focusing on income support, access to institutional credit, rural infrastructure development, livelihood diversification, and enhanced social welfare programs.

Keywords

Farmers, Categories, Consumption Expenditure, Per Capita, Distribution. JEL Codes: C81, E21, Q01, Q12.

Introduction

Consumption patterns provide a significant insight into a household's standard of living. The welfare of a household can be inferred from the quality of its consumption budget, with expansion in consumption potential enhancing lives without diminishing the well-being of others, and fostering vibrant, creative communities and individuals (Bhoi and Sahu, 2015). The structure of daily material life, determined by consumption patterns, both reflects and reinforces economic disparities between social classes. Variations in income structures among different income groups translate directly into distinct consumption behaviors. In economic terms, consumption expenditure refers to the total monetary value of goods and services consumed, including durable goods, food items, and other essentials.

Punjab serves as a notable case study of a fast-developing economy founded upon agriculture. The state's resource base has historically determined the pace and trajectory of economic growth, with agriculture functioning as its backbone (Sidhu, 2002). Although the agricultural sector's share in the state domestic product has declined over time, it still contributes nearly two-fifths of the total output. The Green Revolution, while transformative, was geographically and crop-specific, benefiting states such as Punjab, Haryana, Gujarat, and Uttar Pradesh, and focusing on crops like wheat, rice, and a few other food grains (Sharma, 2012). While its impact in Punjab persisted until the 1980s, signs of stagnation emerged thereafter. In recent decades, Punjab's relative contribution to India's central pool of food grains, especially wheat and paddy, has been declining (Singh & Singh, 2014).

The economic reforms of the 1990s were expected to provide Punjab with a renewed push towards prosperity, building upon the state's earlier agricultural successes. However, the post-reform period saw reversed trends in agriculture, marked by rising costs of cultivation for major crops, reduced profitability, and a deterioration in farmers' socio-economic conditions (Singh & Singh, 2002). These pressures have manifested in low farm incomes, indebtedness, increasing farmer suicides, and the withdrawal of smallholders from farming activities (Vatta, 2007). The causes have been multifaceted, ranging from crop failures and adverse market policies to social challenges and economic distress, all leading to heavy borrowing among farming households.

Despite these challenges, the initial success of the Green Revolution in Punjab significantly increased agricultural output and incomes across different categories of farmers (Vatta, 2012). Consumption expenditure has emerged as a key economic indicator in reflecting the standard of living of farming families, as it depends closely on income levels (Sachdeva & Chahal, 2010). Studying the trends in consumption expenditure among various farmer categories is therefore essential for understanding both economic well-being and inequality.

This study focuses on analyzing the levels and patterns of consumption expenditure among different categories of farmers in the border areas of rural Punjab.

Objective of study

1. To study the levels of consumption expenditure and the per capita consumption expenditure of different farmer categories.
2. To analyze the relative shares of different items of consumption expenditure and examine inequalities in the distribution of consumption expenditure among various categories of farmers.

Review of Literature

Bhoi and Sahu (2015) analysed the income and expenditure pattern of households of Kotpad block Odisha. For the purpose of study, 60 farm households were randomly interviewed using purposive sampling technique. The study revealed that the primary source of income of the farm households was agriculture which contributes 52 per cent to the entire income and remaining 48 per cent income came from the secondary sources. The farm household earned 18 per cent income from the government services, 15 per cent from self-employment and 5 per cent income from the private sector, 3 per cent income from petty business and 4 per cent income from wage labour. The expenditure results reveal that respondents spent the highest portion of their income on food and agriculture, followed by loan repayment and education. Health and personal expenses were comparatively lower, indicating a prioritization of basic needs and financial obligations over discretionary spending. The study suggested that the Government should give main concern to support the peasantry to establish crop wise value addition and processing industries under peasant-worker cooperatives with the support of financial organizations.

Kaur et al. (2015) made an attempt to analyse the income and consumption pattern of cultivators of Punjab. The study was based on the secondary data acquired from the report of Economic and Statistical Organization Punjab. The percentage contribution of farm income was the least in non-mechanized farms and the maximum under mechanized farms. The main component of expenditure in all the categories was food and it decreased with the advancement in technology. Within the food segment, milk and milk products, wheat and sugar had shown a higher proportion in the total food expenditure. The study depicted a same pattern for the different categories with a bias towards high energy food items, but a deficit in protective food materials in farm households of Punjab.

Gupta and Singh (2016) examined the changing pattern of private final consumption expenditure in the rural and urban areas of India, throughout the four decades (1972-73 to 2011-12). The study revealed that there had been a shift in expenditure pattern from traditional food items to non-food items. The proportion of food items remained higher in rural areas as opposed to urban areas. The increasing trend of rising non-food expenditure was evident in both the urban and rural areas. The inter-state investigation further pointed out that there were fewer states above the all-India average in urban areas than rural areas. The most significant change in non-food expenditure over the years had been that the contribution of services and durable goods increased significantly in both rural and urban areas. On the other hand, the share of fuel, light, pan and tobacco and intoxicants had decreased in both the areas.

Kaur and Verma (2018) discussed the structure and pattern of household consumption expenditure in rural and urban areas of Punjab. The study was based on primary data collected from Ludhiana and Faridkot districts of Punjab. Sample of 200 consumers from rural areas was selected randomly to make comparative analyses of structure and pattern of consumption expenditure on food items. The study explored that there were understandable inequalities amongst urban and rural consumers regarding consumption expenditure. However, the allocation of per capita consumption expenditure was to some extent fair in rural areas as opposed to that in urban areas. This finding was also supported by the Gini coefficient. The value of Gini coefficient was 0.4263 and 0.3631 for urban and rural areas, respectively

Singh et al. (2018) studied the expenditure pattern of small, medium and large farmers in Uttar Pradesh for two agricultural years 2004-2006. The study observed that the marginal and small farmers made 78.12 and 73.20 per cent of the total consumption expenditure on food items, respectively while large farmers spend only 66.24 per cent on food items. Next in order was expenditure made on social ceremonies, clothing and housing by the marginal and small

farmers, while large farmers spent the second highest expenditure on education followed by the expenditure on social ceremonies, housing and clothing. The proportion of expenditure on fuel, light, medicine and health was almost equal for all the size groups of farms. The marginal farmers spent more than their income on consumption expenditure while the small and large farmers spent less than their total income.

Kumar et al. (2023) conducted a study in rural Punjab during 2019–20 across eight districts to analyse domestic expenditure patterns among farm households. The objective was to examine the pattern, distribution, and determinants of expenditure across farm size categories. Primary data were collected from 160 households using a three-stage stratified random sampling method. The study applied descriptive statistics, Lorenz curve, Gini coefficient, and multiple regression analysis. Results showed that domestic expenditure increases with farm size, with large farmers spending more than marginal farmers. Food and non-food items had nearly equal shares, while services formed a smaller portion. The Gini coefficients indicated relatively equal distribution of expenditure. Regression results revealed that household size negatively and operational holding positively affected per capita expenditure, suggesting the need for policy support for small farmers.

Singh et al. (2023) examined regional variation in consumption expenditure and nutritional intake in Madhya Pradesh. The study used NSS unit-level data for 2011–12 to analyse inter-regional differences. The objective was to study changes in consumption, compare regions, and identify key determinants. Methodology included descriptive analysis and a two-stage FGLS model. Results revealed significant regional disparities, with the central region having the highest consumption expenditure. Nutritional intake trends were uneven despite rising expenditure. Factors like income, education, household size, and ration card access significantly influenced consumption. The study suggests region-specific policy interventions to reduce disparities and improve welfare.

Singh et al. (2024) analysed consumption expenditure of farm households in Punjab using NSSO data for 2002–03 and 2018–19. The study aimed to examine trends in consumption alongside agrarian changes using CPI-adjusted secondary data. Results show consumption expenditure increased significantly across all farm categories. Overall expenditure rose from ₹51,475 to ₹153,565, reflecting improved living standards. However, expenditure grew faster than income, indicating financial stress and dependence on credit. The study suggests policy measures such as improved credit access, income support, and financial security for farmers to reduce vulnerability.

Methodology

The present study is based on primary data collected from the different categories of farmers residing in the border areas of rural Punjab. A three-stage sampling technique was employed to ensure representativeness and reliability. Six border districts namely Amritsar, Fazilka, Ferozepur, Gurdaspur, Pathankot, and Tarn Taran were purposively selected due to their proximity to the international border with Pakistan. All development blocks located within 10 kilometers of the international border in Punjab were selected purposely as the area of study. There are 20 development blocks which lie on the international border. All 20 development blocks were selected as the primary area of investigation. In the second stage, one village was randomly selected from each of these 20 border-adjointing blocks. A representative proportional sample of 30 per cent of farmers from each category was randomly selected for the survey. A total of 423 farm households were selected for the survey across all 20 villages. Out of 423 selected farm households, 134 farmers belong to the category of marginal farmers, 137 to small farmers, 82 to semi-medium farmers, 54 to medium farmers and 16 to large farmers.

Descriptive statistical tools such as mean, percentage, and ratios were used to determine average and per capita consumption expenditure, while the Average Propensity to Consume (APC) was calculated to examine expenditure-income relationships. Inequality in consumption expenditure across landholding categories was assessed using the Gini Coefficient.

Result and Discussion

Levels of Consumption Expenditure of Farmers:

Human life is sustained by consumption. By increasing people's capacities and improving their quality of life, consumption advances human development (Geetha, 2011). The income level and hence the consumption expenditure of the farm households differ due to the assets they own. In rural areas, the ownership of land acts as a security against the contingencies of life. Hence, the farm households generally have greater consumption expenditure due to more income from land.

Table 1 highlights that an average farm household spends Rs.540090.07 annually on consumption. The annual consumption expenditure across farmer categories demonstrates a positive relationship between farm size and overall spending. The large farmers incur the

highest annual expenditure (Rs. 12,10,431.25), while marginal farmers spend the least (Rs. 3,55,649.25). An average sampled farm household spends Rs.247387.08 on non-durables, Rs.68182.96 on durables and Rs.119250.13 on services, and Rs. 105266.9 on socio-religious rituals every year. The maximum consumption expenditure on nondurable items is made by the medium farmers of Rs.401187.05 per annum and the minimum expenditure on non-durable items is spent by the marginal farmers of Rs.179520.16 per annum. The maximum consumption expenditure on non-durable items is spent on milk and milk products by all the categories of farmers. An average sampled farmer spends Rs.73344. 92 on milk and milk products. This amount is Rs.59129.85, Rs.68353.28 ,78069.51, Rs. 110477. 78 and Rs.85600 per annum for the marginal, small, semi-medium, medium and large farmers, respectively. The highest spending among non-durables is on milk and milk products—which is consistent with Singh et al. (2020), reinforcing the centrality of dairy in Punjab farm household budgets. The expenditure on food grains is the highest for the medium farmers amounting to Rs.38927.78 per annum, while the minimum expenditure of Rs.28178.83 annually is spent by the small farmers. The maximum expenditure on fruits is spent by the medium farmers and the maximum expenditures on vegetables is spent by the large farmers per annum. Conversely, the marginal farmers spent the minimum on fruits and vegetables.

Table1: Levels of Consumption Expenditure of Farmers (Mean Values, In Rs., Per Annum)

Sr. No.	Items of Consumption	Marginal Farmers	Small Farmers	Semi-Medium Farmers	Medium Farmers	Large Farmers	All Sampled Farmers
Non-Durables							
1	Food Grains	29253.73	28178.83	32500	38927.78	28250	30731.92
2	Spices	10776.12	12670.8	13963.41	16931.48	12706.25	12866.43
3	Fruits	7391.79	10002.92	11939.02	17764.82	16606.25	10791.73
4	Vegetables	8130.6	9586.13	11481.71	17766.67	18268.75	10865.25
5	Milk and milk products	59129.85	68353.28	78069.51	110477.8	85600	73344.92
6	Edible oils	5173.88	6668.61	7807.32	9992.59	7887.5	6886.29
7	Sugarcane	2956.72	3501.46	3768.29	4998.15	3656.25	3577.54
8	Meat/egg	880.6	1574.45	7268.29	3916.67	9750	3066.67
9	Tea leaves	4952.24	5835.04	6524.39	8883.33	6725	6111.82
10	Biscuits/bread	4118.66	6508.76	6602.44	6987.04	8925	5922.22
11	Pickle	1404.48	1500.73	1837.81	2000	1500	1599.29
12	Fuel/electricity	22071.64	30331.38	52092.68	73500	49743.75	38178.49
13	Clothing	9928.36	13347.45	22026.83	31333.33	48250	17563.12
14	Washing articles	4576.87	5884.67	9185.36	20000	18681.25	8396.22
15	Footwear	2958.21	4315.33	9225.61	22222.22	24912.5	7902.36
16	Intoxicants and drugs	3993.28	5340.88	7853.66	10225.93	19500	6560.28
17	Others	1823.13	1744.53	4323.17	5259.26	9875	3025.53
	Sub-total	179520.2	215345.3	286469.5	401187.1	370837.5	247387.1
Durables							
1	House construction	39067.16	25772.99	43800	39722.22	127812.5	37852.24
2	Tv/Lcd	317.16	843.79	858.54	1429.63	0	722.7
3	Watches	11.19	15.33	50	175.93	425	56.74
4	Cooler/AC	335.82	1455.47	725.61	3481.48	8437.5	1482.03
5	Furniture	190.29	153.28	790.24	87.04	0	274.23
	Utensils	14.93	57.66	0	0	0	23.4
7	Car/jeep	1477.62	9035.77	27000	41296.3	168750	20283.45
8	Motorcycles	1667.91	838.69	493.9	7305.56	15187.5	2402.84
9	Refrigerator	100.75	178.83	380.49	259.26	2112.5	276.59

10	Washing machine	143.28	115.33	280.49	0	0	137.12
11	Gas geyser	0	0	158.54	1759.26	425	271.39
12	Almirah	429.1	0	50	159.26	42187.5	1761.7
13	Inverter	0	0	798.78	0	2281.25	241.13
14	Sewing machine	129.1	0	243.9	1750	0	311.58
15	Computer/ laptop	485.07	0	841.46	3055.56	2956.25	818.68
	Sub-total	44379.19	38467.14	76471.95	100481.5	370575	68182.96
Services							
1	Education	35446.27	54934.31	67939.02	117148.2	86062.5	60401.42
2	Healthcare	7181.34	15343.07	27195.12	38657.41	19200	18177.31
3	Conveyance / transport	13843.28	29043.79	41097.56	64894.44	49612.5	31919.86
4	Communication	5675.37	7043.8	8560.98	10592.59	11687.5	7533.1
5	Entertainment	628.36	765.69	1585.37	2685.19	3206.25	1218.44
	Sub-total	62774.62	107130.7	146378.1	233977.8	169768.8	119250.1
Socio-Religious Rituals							
1	Marriage/other	52708.95	54598.54	100622	188309.3	230400	86640.89
2	Religious ceremonies	16276.13	13295.63	28817.08	7624.07	68850	18626.01
	Sub-total	68985.08	67894.17	129439	195932.3	299250	105266.9
	Total	355649.3	428837.2	638758.5	931579.7	1210431	540090.1

Source: Field Survey, 2021-22

The large farmers spent the maximum amount on durable items, with expenditures reaching to Rs. 370575 per annum, while the small farmers spent the minimum of (Rs.38467.14 annually) on durables. Among durable items, the marginal, small, and semi-medium farmers allocated their maximum expenditures to housing, with respective figures of Rs. 39067.16, Rs. 25722.99, and Rs. 43500 per annum respectively. On four wheelers, the maximum expenditure is spent by the large farmers followed by the medium farmers. The semi-medium farmers lead in expenditure on washing machines. The highest expenditure on computer laptops is spent by the medium farmers, followed by the large, semi-medium and marginal farmers, while the small farmers recorded no expenditure on this item.

The maximum consumption expenditure of Rs.233977.78 per annum is spent on services by the medium farmers, and the minimum expenditure of Rs.62774.62 per year on services is made by the marginal farmers. The medium farmers lead in expenditure on education, spending Rs.117148.15 annually, while the marginal farmers allocate Rs.35446.27 per year to education. The medium farmers spend the highest amount of Rs.38657.41 per annum on healthcare and the minimal spending of Rs.7181.34 is by the marginal farmers. The large farmers lead in spending on communication and entertainment, while the marginal farmers spend the minimum. On an average, the farm households spend Rs.105266.9 on celebration of socio-religious ceremonies. The large farmers spend the maximum expenditure on socio-religious activities followed by the medium farmers.

The above analysis illustrates the varying consumption expenditure levels across the different categories of farmers, with a particular focus on non-durable items. Expenditure on non-durable items, especially milk and milk products, dominates across all groups. The large farmers lead in spending on durable goods, services, and socio-religious activities, reflecting their higher income levels and capacity for discretionary consumption. The maximum expenditure incurred on all the items by the large farmers reveals that ownership of means of production has its important role in determining the farmers' levels of living. The consumption expenditure of the large farmers is found to be 3.40 times the consumption expenditure of the marginal farmers. This aligns with Bihari and Sidhu (2019), who observed a strong positive correlation between farm size and consumption levels in rural Punjab, with larger landholders also allocating more resources to durables and socio-religious functions while marginal and small farmers spend mainly on basic needs.

Pattern of Consumption Expenditure of Farmers:

The percentage of each item of consumption in total consumption expenditure provides a better understanding of the standard of life of each population segment. According to the Engel Law, a person's expenditure on food goods decreases as their income rises, but their expenditure on non-food and other items increases. He claims that while the wealthy segments spend more on consumption in absolute terms, their proportion spending decreases, indicating that they are able to spend comparatively bigger portions on other things that raise their standard of living and well-being. Since the average consumption levels of different farm-size categories are not the same in the border areas of rural Punjab, the consumption pattern can better be studied by comparing the relative shares of individual items of consumption in the total consumption expenditure of different farm-size categories. Table 2 shows the pattern of consumption expenditure of farm households in border areas of rural Punjab. On average, a farm household expends 45.81 per cent of their total budget on non-durable items, 12.63 per cent on durables, 22.08 per cent on services, and 19.48 per cent annually on socio-religious rituals in border areas of rural Punjab. The marginal farmers allocate the highest 50.49 per cent of their total consumption expenditure on non-durable items, followed by the small (50.22 per cent), semi-medium (44.85 per cent), medium (43.08 per cent), and large (30.64 per cent) farmers. The data highlights that the highest share of expenditure among the non-durable items is allocated to milk and milk products (13.58 per cent). The marginal farmers spent the highest 16.63 per cent of their total expenditure on this item. The small farmers closely follow with 15.94 per cent share, while large farmers allocate only 7.07 per cent, indicating a marked difference in dairy consumption across the categories. This preference underscores the significance of dairy in their diets. The survey has revealed that the different agricultural production activities require hard labour. As a result, the farmers rear some milch animals; and the proportion of this consumption item is the highest among the non-durables items.

Table 2: Pattern of Consumption Expenditure of Farmers: Category-wise

Sr No.	Item of Consumption	Marginal Farmers	Small Farmers	Semi-Medium Farmers	Medium Farmers	Large Farmers	All Sampled Farmers
Non- Durables							
1	Foodgrains	8.22	6.57	5.09	4.18	2.33	5.69
2	Spices	3.03	2.95	2.19	1.82	1.05	2.38
3	Fruits	2.08	2.33	1.87	1.91	1.37	2.00
4	Vegetables	2.29	2.24	1.80	1.91	1.51	2.01
5	Milk and milk products	16.63	15.94	12.22	11.86	7.07	13.58
6	Edible oils	1.45	1.56	1.22	1.07	0.65	1.28
7	Sugarcane	0.83	0.82	0.59	0.54	0.30	0.66
8	Meat/egg	0.25	0.37	1.14	0.42	0.81	0.57
9	Tea leaves	1.39	1.36	1.02	0.95	0.56	1.13
10	Biscuits/bread	1.16	1.52	1.03	0.75	0.74	1.10
11	Pickle	0.39	0.35	0.29	0.21	0.12	0.30
12	Fuel/electricity	6.21	7.07	8.16	7.89	4.11	7.07
13	Clothing	2.79	3.11	3.45	3.36	3.99	3.25
14	Washing articles	1.29	1.37	1.44	2.15	1.54	1.55
15	Footwear	0.83	1.01	1.44	2.39	2.06	1.46
16	Intoxicants and drugs	1.12	1.25	1.23	1.10	1.61	1.21
17	Others	0.51	0.41	0.68	0.56	0.82	0.56
	Sub-total	50.49	50.22	44.85	43.08	30.64	45.81
Durables							
1	House construction	10.98	6.01	6.86	4.27	10.56	7.24
2	Tv/Lcd	0.09	0.20	0.13	0.15	0.00	0.13
3	Watches	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.01
4	Cooler/AC	0.09	0.34	0.11	0.37	0.70	0.27
5	Furniture	0.05	0.04	0.12	0.01	0.00	0.05

6	Utensils	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	Car/jeep	0.42	2.11	4.23	4.43	13.94	3.76
8	Motorcycles	0.46	0.20	0.08	0.78	1.25	0.44
9	Refrigerator	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.03	0.17	0.05
10	Washing machine	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.03
1	Gas geyser	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.19	0.04	0.05
12	Almirah	0.12	0.00	0.01	0.02	3.49	0.33
13	Inverter	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.19	0.04
14	Sewing machine	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.19	0.00	0.06
15	Computer/ laptop	0.14	0.00	0.13	0.33	0.24	0.15
	Sub-total	12.47	8.97	11.97	10.79	30.62	12.63
Services							
1	Education	9.97	12.81	10.64	12.58	7.11	11.18
2	Healthcare	2.02	3.58	4.26	4.15	1.59	3.37
3	Conveyance/transport	3.89	6.77	6.43	6.94	4.10	5.91
4	Communication	1.60	1.64	1.34	1.14	0.97	1.39
5	Entertainment	0.18	0.18	0.25	0.28	0.26	0.23
	Sub-total	17.65	24.98	22.92	25.09	14.03	22.08
Social-Religious Rituals							
1	Marriage/other	14.82	12.73	15.75	20.22	19.03	16.03
2	Religious ceremonies	4.58	3.10	4.51	0.82	5.69	3.45
	Sub- total	19.40	15.83	20.26	21.04	24.72	19.48
	Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Calculated from Table 1

An average sampled farmer spends 7.07 per cent on fuel and electricity. The semi-medium farmers allocate the highest percentage of 8.16 per cent on fuel and electricity, the medium farmers followed with 7.89 per cent while this share for the small, marginal and large farmers is 7.07, 6.21 and 4.11 per cent, respectively. The next important item is foodgrains contributing 5.69 per cent to the total consumption expenditure. The marginal farmers allocate the highest percentage of 8.22 per cent for food grains, closely followed by the small, semi-medium medium and large farmers. This shows that as farm size increases, the proportion spent on food-grains decreases. The next important item is clothing contributing 3.25 per cent to the total consumption expenditure of an average farmer. This proportion increases as farm size increases. The large farmers allocate about 4 per cent to clothing items, indicating a greater spending on clothing compared to smaller farmers. This data underscores that the marginal farmers allocate the highest percentage of their expenditure to non-durable goods, despite their lower absolute spending compared to other categories, reflecting their lower income levels compared to the large farmers.

The percentage of total consumption expenditure on durable items is 12.63 per cent by the average sampled farmer. The maximum expenditure on durable consumption items is made by the large farmers (30.62), and this share for the marginal, small, semi-medium and medium farmers is 12.47, 8.97, 11.97, 10.79 per cent, respectively. Expenditure on house construction accounts for the largest percentage of total consumption expenditure among durable items; as on average, farmers spent 7.24 per cent of their expenditure. This share is 10.98 per cent for the marginal farmers followed by the large, semi-medium, small and medium farmers with respective percentages of 10.56, 6.86, 6.01 and 4.27 per cent. The large farmers allocate the highest (13.94 per cent) percentage of their total consumption expenditure on durable items to cars or jeeps. While the medium farmers, meanwhile, allocate 4.43 per cent of their total consumption expenditure to cars or jeeps.

Slightly more than 22 per cent of total spending is spent on services. This proportion is as high as 25.09 and 24.98 per cent for the medium and small farmers, respectively. The sampled farmers spend the maximum percentage of services expenditure on education. The small

farmers spend 12.81 per cent of their total consumption expenditure on education, followed by the medium farmers with 12.58 per cent. The large farmers allocate the least 7.11 per cent on education. The consumption expenditure on healthcare is 4.26 per cent for the semi-medium farmers followed by the medium (4.15 per cent) and small farmers (3.58 per cent). An average sampled farmer spends 19.48 per cent of total expenditure on socio-religious rituals. This proportion is the highest (24.72 per cent) for the large farmers, followed by the medium, semi-medium, marginal and small farmers. An average farmer spends 16.03 per cent of total expenditure on marriages, and 3.45 per cent on religious ceremonies. The proportion of consumption expenditure on religious ceremonies is the highest for the large farmers followed by the marginal, semi-medium, small and medium farmers.

The expenditure patterns across farmer categories reflect significant variations in spending habits and priorities. The marginal and small farmers allocate a substantial percentage to non-durable goods despite lower overall expenditure, emphasizing their economic constraints. The dominance of non-durables in the spending pattern, especially by the marginal and small farmers (over 50%), is echoed by Sidhu (2019) and Singh et al. (2020), who found that resource-poor groups dedicate a disproportionate share of limited budgets to subsistence, leaving little for durables and services. The large farmers lead in durable item spending, particularly on houses and cars/jeeps, highlighting their higher income levels and investment capacity. The larger farmers' greater share on socio-religious and durable expenses further underscores the importance of income and asset base in shaping discretionary consumption, a finding also drawn by Kumar (2022).

Per Capita Consumption Expenditure of Farmers

So far emphasis has been on the analysis of absolute amounts and percentages of various items of consumption expenditure incurred by the different farm-size categories in border areas of rural Punjab. Since the family size of different farm-size categories varies, it becomes relevant to study the per capita consumption expenditure of the different farm-size categories. Table 3 reveals that the per capita consumption expenditure of an average farm household is Rs. 108889.1 and the per capita annual expenditure increases with farm size. The marginal farmers spend Rs. 76,156.16 per capita annually, rising to Rs. 2,36,412.35 among the large farmers. Non-durables and milk products again represent substantial shares, while durable goods and services are favored by those with larger holdings. Findings confirm that per capita consumption rises substantially with farm size, similar to the trends reported by Singh et al. (2020) and Kumar (2022), who noted that marginal and small farmers' per capita expenditure barely covers necessities, exposing them to vulnerability and periodic indebtedness.

Table 3: Per Capita Consumption Expenditure of Farmers (In Rs., Per Annum)

Sr No.	Item of Consumption	Marginal Farmers	Small Farmers	Semi-Medium Farmers	Medium Farmers	Large Farmers	All Sampled Farmers
Non- Durables							
1	Foodgrains	6264.18	5798.11	6372.55	6817.47	5517.58	6195.95
2	Spices	2307.52	2607.16	2737.92	2965.23	2481.69	2594.04
3	Fruits	1582.83	2058.21	2340.99	3111.18	3243.41	2175.75
4	Vegetables	1741.03	1972.46	2251.32	3111.50	3568.12	2190.57
5	Milk and milk products	12661.64	14064.46	15307.75	19348.12	16718.75	14787.28
6	Edible oils	1107.90	1372.14	1530.85	1750.02	1540.53	1388.37
7	Sugarcane	633.13	720.47	738.88	875.33	714.11	721.28
8	Meat/egg	188.56	323.96	1425.16	685.93	1904.30	618.28
9	Tea leaves	1060.44	1200.63	1279.29	1555.75	1313.48	1232.22

10	Biscuits/bread	881.94	1339.25	1294.60	1223.65	1743.16	1194.00
11	Pickle	300.74	308.79	360.35	350.26	292.97	322.44
12	Fuel/electricity	4726.26	6241.03	10214.25	12872.15	9715.58	7697.28
13	Clothing	2125.99	2746.39	4318.99	5487.45	9423.83	3540.95
14	Washing articles	980.06	1210.84	1801.05	3502.63	3648.68	1692.79
15	Footwear	633.45	887.93	1808.94	3891.81	4865.72	1593.22
16	Intoxicants and drugs	855.09	1098.95	1539.93	1790.88	3808.59	1322.64
17	Others	390.39	358.96	847.68	921.06	1928.71	609.99
	Sub-total	38441.15	44309.72	56170.49	70260.42	72429.20	49877.00
Durables							
1	House construction	8365.56	5303.09	8588.24	6956.61	24963.38	7886.97
2	LcdTv	67.92	73.62	168.34	50.37	0.00	145.70
3	Watches	2.40	3.15	9.80	30.81	83.01	11.44
4	Cooler/AC	71.91	299.48	142.28	609.72	1647.95	298.80
5	Furniture	40.75	31.54	154.95	15.24	0.00	55.29
6	Utensils	3.20	11.87	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.72
7	Car/jeep	316.41	1859.21	5294.12	7232.28	32958.98	4089.41
8	Motorcycles	357.15	172.57	96.84	1279.43	2966.31	484.44
9	Refrigerator	21.57	6.80	74.61	45.40	412.60	55.77
10	Washing machine	30.68	23.73	55.00	0.00	0.00	27.64
11	Gas geyser	0.00	0.00	31.09	308.10	83.01	54.72
12	Almirah	91.89	0.00	9.80	27.89	8239.75	355.18
13	Inverter	0.00	0.00	156.62	0.00	445.56	48.62
14	Sewing machine	27.65	0.00	47.82	306.48	0.00	62.82
15	Computer/laptop	103.87	0.00	164.99	535.12	577.39	165.06
	Sub-total	9500.96	7915.05	14994.50	17597.46	72377.93	13746.58
Services							
1	Education	7590.21	11303.36	13321.38	20516.31	16809.08	12177.71
2	Healthcare	1537.76	3157.01	5332.38	6770.12	3750.00	3664.78

3	Conveyance/ transport	2964.30	5976.09	8058.35	11365.05	9689.94	6435.46
4	Communication	1215.28	1449.34	1678.62	1855.10	2282.71	1518.77
5	Entertainment	134.55	157.55	310.86	470.26	626.22	245.65
	Sub-total	13442.10	22043.35	28701.58	40976.84	33157.96	24042.37
Socio-religious Rituals							
1	Marriage/ other	11286.71	11234.27	19729.79	32978.85	45000.00	7467.92
2	Religious ceremonies	3485.25	2735.71	5650.44	1335.23	13447.27	3755.24
	Sub- total	14771.95	13969.98	25380.23	34314.08	58447.27	21223.16
	Total	76156.16	88238.11	125246.8	163148.8	236412.35	108889.1

Source: Calculations from Table 1

The per capita consumption expenditure pattern of the farmers is closely related to the household consumption expenditure pattern across the different categories of farmers. It is directly related to the farm size; larger the farm size more is the per capita consumption expenditure. Since the family size varies from one category to the other, there are some differences in the range of per capita and per household consumption expenditure. The per capita consumption expenditure of the large farmers is 3.10 times and per household consumption expenditure is 3.40 times of the marginal farmers. These findings underscore the varying economic behaviors and consumption patterns across farmer categories, highlighting the need for tailored policies and interventions in agricultural development and rural welfare programs. Understanding these expenditure dynamics is crucial for policymakers aiming to address disparities and promote equitable economic growth in rural communities.

Average Propensity to Consume of Farmers:

Average propensity to consume is a measure used in economics to indicate what portion of income is spent on consumption. The average propensity to consume is calculated by dividing average consumption expenditure by average farm family income. Table.4 reveals that the average propensity to consume is estimated at 1.13 for an average farm household. It is the highest (1.27) for the marginal farmers, followed by the small (1.27), semi-medium (1.17), medium (0.95) and large farmers (0.94). The average propensity to consume being above unity for the marginal, small, and semi-medium farmers demonstrates that these groups routinely spend beyond their annual incomes largely through borrowing a phenomenon widely acknowledged by Bihari and Sidhu (2019) and Singh et al. (2020). The medium and large farmers, conversely, have an APC below 1, reflecting surplus income generation and savings.

Table 4: Average Propensity to Consume of Farmers: Category-wise

Description	Marginal Farmers	Small Farmers	Semi-Medium Farmers	Medium Farmers	Large Farmers	All Sampled Farmers
Consumption (\bar{c})	355649.25	428837.23	638758.54	931579.66	1210431.25	540090.07
Income (\bar{y})	280723.88	346379.56	545439.02	976703.70	1279687.50	479938.53
Average propensity to consume (\bar{c}/\bar{y})	1.27	1.24	1.17	0.95	0.94	1.13

Source: Calculations from Table 1

The marginal, small, and semi-medium farmer categories are found to be underneath the deficit in the border areas of rural Punjab. The marginal, small, and semi-medium farmer categories have to accomplish their necessities by obtaining loans from institutional and non-institutional sources for the reason that their average income is insufficient to meet their everyday expenditure; and saving in reality is not easy for them. In distinction, the medium and large farmer categories have surplus income as they possess huge land holdings and other dynamic possessions.

Distribution of Consumption Expenditure of Farmers:

Table .5 highlights significant disparities in the distribution of consumption expenditure among the different categories of farmers in the border areas of rural Punjab. The figures show a significant disparity in the distribution of consumption expenditure among the different categories of farm households. The bottom 10 per cent of farm households appear to have a disproportionately low (2.57 per cent) share of total consumption expenditure, while the top 10 per cent average farm households has a much higher (33.70 per cent) share. The bottom 10 per cent of the semi-medium farmers account for only 3.56 per cent of the total consumption expenditure, whereas the top 10 per cent retain 34.39 per cent of the total consumption expenditure. The bottom 10 per cent of the small and marginal farmers share 3.60, and 4.04 per cent of total expenditure, respectively, whereas the top 10 per cent of small and marginal farmers share 26.63 and 25.89 per cent of the total consumption expenditure, respectively. The same trend can be seen in the case of the bottom 10 per cent of the medium and large farmer category, as they account 3.91 and 3.19 per cent of total consumption expenditure.

Table 5: Distribution of Consumption Expenditure of Farmers

Cumulative Percentage of Households	Marginal Farmers	Small Farmers	Semi-Medium Farmers	Medium Farmers	Large Farmers	All sampled Farmers
10.00	4.04	3.60	3.56	3.91	3.19	2.57
20.00	8.23	8.40	8.15	8.88	6.95	6.16
30.00	13.01	14.26	13.53	14.76	11.69	10.66
40.00	18.35	21.01	19.66	20.96	17.06	16.07
50.00	28.49	28.61	26.41	27.80	24.75	22.64
60.00	38.39	37.41	34.03	35.21	34.20	30.24
70.00	48.54	46.90	42.64	43.58	45.15	39.52
80.00	59.02	58.19	52.95	54.09	57.59	50.90
90.00	74.11	73.37	65.61	69.67	73.65	66.30
100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Gini Coefficient	0.32	0.32	0.37	0.34	0.35	0.41

Source: Field Survey, 2021-22

If we compare the bottom 40 per cent of farmers with the top 10 per cent of farmers, we find that the bottom 40 per cent of the marginal, small, semi-medium, medium, and large farmers share 18.35, 21.01, 19.66, 20.96, 17.06 per cent of the total consumption expenditure. This share is less than the share of the top 10 per cent of farmers among all the categories of farmers. The share of the top ten percent of the marginal, small, semi-medium, medium, and large farmers in total consumption expenditure is 25.89, 26.63, 34.39, 30.33, and 26.35 per cent, respectively. The pronounced disparity, with the richest decile spending more than the

bottom 40 percent, mirrors the conclusions of Kumar (2022). The table highlights that the distribution of farmers’ consumption is highly unequal among the semi-medium farmers as compared to other categories of farmers. The value of the Gini coefficient is the highest (0.37) for the semi-medium farmers, followed by the large farmers (0.35). The value of the Gini coefficient for the small farmers, medium farmers, and marginal farmers is 0.32, 0.34, 0.32, respectively.

The data highlights the uneven distribution of wealth and resources within the agricultural sector, which can have significant implications for rural livelihoods and economic development in the border areas of rural Punjab. Efforts to address these disparities may involve policies aimed at providing greater support and resources to small-scale farmers, improving access to credit, and promoting more equitable land distribution.

Distribution of Per Capita Consumption Expenditure of Farmers

The data from Table 6 further underscores the disparities in the distribution of per capita consumption expenditure among the different categories of farmers in the border areas of rural Punjab. The figures show significant disparities in the distribution of per capita consumption expenditure among the different categories of farm households. The bottom 10 per cent of the sampled farm population appear to have a disproportionately low (3.18 percent) share of per capita consumption expenditure, while the top 10 per cent has a much higher (32.98 per cent) share.

Table 6: Distribution of Per Capita Consumption Expenditure of Farmers

Cumulative Percentage of Person	Marginal Farmers	Small Farmers	Semi-Medium Farmers	Medium Farmers	Large Farmers	All Sampled Farmers
10	4.12	4.98	5.01	4.31	4.08	3.18
20	8.50	10.41	10.72	9.57	8.78	7.28
30	13.11	16.43	16.67	15.45	12.05	12.06
40	18.93	22.98	21.03	21.58	19.38	17.75
50	29.11	30.33	27.05	27.96	26.45	24.24
60	39.37	39.15	36.71	35.87	35.97	31.92
70	48.81	48.75	45.27	43.64	44.73	41.04
80	59.63	59.59	55.76	54.50	55.60	51.98
90	74.32	73.05	68.03	69.44	74.71	67.02
100	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Gini Coefficient	0.31	0.29	0.33	0.33	0.34	0.39

Source: Field Survey, 2021-22

The bottom 10 per cent of the population of small and semi-medium farmers share almost the same percentage of per capita expenditure i.e. 4.89 and 5.01 percent respectively, whereas the top 10 percent population of the small and semi-medium farmers account 26.95 and 31.97 percent of the total per capita consumption expenditure respectively. The same trend can be seen in the case of the bottom 10 per cent of the medium and large farmer category, as they share 4.31 and 5.08 per cent of total per capita consumption expenditure. If we compare the bottom 40 per cent population of farmers with the top 10 per cent of farmers, we find that the share of the top 10 per cent population of farmers is larger among all the categories of farmers. The table highlights that the distribution of farmers’ per capita consumption is slightly unequal among the large farmers as compared to other categories of farmers; as the value of the Gini coefficient is the highest (0.34) for the large farmers, followed by the medium farmers (0.33).

The value of the Gini coefficient for the semi- medium, marginal and small farmers is 0.33, 0.31, 0.29 respectively. The data shows significant disparity in consumption among the different categories of farmers, with large farmers facing the highest level of inequality. The Gini coefficient provides a numerical measure of this inequality, with higher values indicating greater disparity. The distribution of per capita consumption, with bottom deciles accounting for a fraction of total spending and relatively high Gini coefficients for large farm households, matches the pattern detailed by Singh et al. (2020) and Kumar (2022): income and consumption disparities are entrenched and linked directly with landholding and occupational structure.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that consumption expenditure among farmers in the border areas of rural Punjab increases with farm size, reflecting significant disparities in both levels and patterns of spending on non-durable goods, durables, services, and socio-religious activities. The marginal and small farmers allocate a larger share of their limited resources to basic necessities, particularly food and dairy, and exhibit higher average propensities to consume, often exceeding their reported incomes—a finding consistent with prior research by Singh et al. (2020) and Kumar (2022). On the other hand, large farm households enjoy higher absolute and per capita expenditures and allocate more to durables, services, and social obligations, echoing trends noted by Bihari and Sidhu (2019). The study exposes marked income and expenditure inequalities, with sharp differences in the shares of the bottom and top deciles, evidenced by high Gini coefficients. These findings highlight persistent disparities in rural consumption patterns that mirror the structural heterogeneity of Punjab's agriculture sector.

Policy Suggestions

To address these disparities and foster inclusive rural development, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

- Strengthen targeted support systems for marginal and small farmers through region-specific income augmenting programs, including support for high-value crops, livestock, and allied sectors, as suggested by Kumar (2022).
- Expand access to affordable institutional credit and create safety nets to reduce the dependency of vulnerable groups on informal borrowing, as Bihari and Sidhu (2019) recommend.
- Reinforce rural infrastructure investments and public expenditure stability to buffer shocks and ensure equitable economic opportunities, as per findings from recent policy analysis.
- Promote non-farm income sources through rural entrepreneurship, skill development, and agro-processing, diversifying livelihoods and reducing inequalities.
- Ensure robust implementation and outreach for existing government welfare schemes, food security programs, and social insurance, focusing on effective delivery and monitoring among the poorest and most vulnerable rural populations.
- Encourage educational and extension programs to enhance financial literacy and prudent consumption planning among rural households.

In sum, a combination of inclusive policy measures, institutional reforms, and improved delivery systems is essential to narrow consumption inequalities and elevate living standards of small and marginal farmers in rural Punjab.

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